

SHAZAR STONE (HAQUIKE): INDIAN SHAZAR HERITAGE IS IN THE DECLINE STAGE¹

Uma Shankar Yadav¹

E-mail: usyadav@mnnit.ac.in

Orchid: 0000-0002-5855-0983

Ravindra Tripathi²

E-mail: ravindra@mnnit.ac.in

Gyan Prakash yadav³

E-mail: gyanprakashacte@gmail.com

Mano Ashis Tripathi³

E-mail: manoashish@gmail.com

³Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon open university Phaphamau Prayagraj India
^{1,2,4}Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology Allahabad Prayagraj India

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6444126

ABSTRACT

All of us know that handicraft product is commonly made by hand or by with the help of handmade tool. in this process, hand skilled people artisan creates different design products theirs decorative and used as utility product like as from Rockwood like shazar stone of Banda which semiprecious stone after diamond, claystone and may more and many more using simple and cheap tools from the time of immemorial, India is called for it handmade made decorative addition industrial country and famous in India These types of items produced are known as handicrafts as they are prepared solely by hands and there is nothing od least technology used in this industry. it is also known for its cultural customer and India feature among the topmost rated cultural country which is famous in the world there is some skilled labor are busy in the world which has and has artisan have added to them and there is nothing any use of machinery. In the following article, we will read about some of the handicrafts of India that you can take back objective of the article to study the shazar stone, its value in our tradition, why declining this industry and suggest strategies for reviving shazar stone.

Keywords: shazar stone, heritage, decline stage

* Received 01.01.2022; Accepted & Published 28.03.2022. Citation: Yadav U.S., Ravindra T., Gyan P. Yadav, Mano A. T. (2022). Shazar stone (haquike): Indian shazar heritage is in the decline stage. *Journal of Language and Literature*, 13(1), p.26-34. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6444126

Introduction

A nature's gift to mankind this Stone is a geological wonder with very high geological value. During the volcanic age of earth when everything was in liquid and semisolid form, the liquid minerals (mostly Manganese and Iron) get deposited within the layers of silicon oxide (Agate) in such a way that they created so many types of patterns. Like shrubs, trees animals & scenes giving it uniqueness. Geologically it is of Quartz family stone in the category of agate with the hardness of seven on Moh's scale nearer to sapphire. Though it is categorized as a semi-precious stone all the three qualities of precious stone are found in it, that is rarity, stability & grace.

There are myths about this stone that it gives strength & mental ounce to the wearer & minter piece to the wearer & even ALL MIGHTY IS pleased with him; It is revered as a holy stone by Islamic communities and a good Talisman for the people who wear it.

History

About four hundred years ago Nawab of Banda (Son of Raja chhatrasal courtesan mustang patronized a "Song Trash" (stone cutter) Ramdas for his artistic stone cutter rends for his artistic stone & jeweler work Once while passing through a village on his regular tour rends had an urge for tobacco smoking one of the villagers provided him a stone chip and Iron strip with COTTON to lit the fire the artistic Ramada saw a very unique pattern in the stone while using it. He collected some more pieces of stones and applied his crafty to them;" LO" he found beautiful patterns on them. He mounted them in silver & gold and presented them to his Nawab who honoured in for it. It was the begging of the "shear stone "(stone with a pattern of trees in them) craft of Banda.

Method of making Shazar stone:

It is crafted nib a very old traditional fashion with awoken bow bad a thin steel wire as a string called "KAMAN". Stones are mounted over a wooden stone called " KHUNTA and sliced by this bow with the help of silicon carbide powder in 2 to 4 mm. thickness These stone slices are then designed, trimmed shaped, and polished with utmost care and precision as the depositions are in micron thickness only

The stone of glory the stone of wonder and infinite history, it's ajar

Banda city of Shazar has discovered in the band a district of the Bundelkhand region about 400 years ago in Banda. The one who discovered it was an Arab man. Arab was memorized its important color full pattern that looks like leaves and trees like structure sometimes time moon, hen, lord Vishnu, Monkey, cloud different decorative flower structure are set up on the ajar star it is natural print so he named it shazar in Arabic .in India n language hair or asphaltic in the Hindi language.

Due to its shins and uniqueness and religious value linkage, the stone is exported to foreign countries people but due unwillingness of the Indian government and Uttar Pradesh government behaviour the export of sugar stone has been declined sharply (Lisa M. Grobar, 2019), as we know that it is a small industry and there is maximum demand of this stone in Muslim country y but less local demand there is nothing value or less value in India even the stone is popular in middle east country like as barren Saudi Arab, Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Israel, and this ensure cent percent success of export program if promoted properly as per the regulation of exporters hajj pilgrims from all over the world shear stone written Quran eat at Saudi Arabia, that is exported from Banda the Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh through agents (Chicherov A., 1970). This semi-precious stone of glory and beauty should get its worthy praise and fame. There is a need for some extra and major boost to this stone but without the help of the govt, it seems near impossible to export to get fame in the.

Sazar the identity of Banda, glory of Kane river, the Bundelkhand region

Figure 1. Showing natural shazar stone picture taken by author during craft fair in prayagraj india .

is called as dendrite agate.it is a homogenous stone and is found in various patterns and colours. These agates are basically of four types. Depend on the different structure.

1. Plane (Agate)
2. Ring
3. Lenin
4. Dendrite

And this agate is also known as tree agate and fungus agate this is found in Banda s ken river on the bank of Banda district in the Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh the specific character of hazard stone is its colourful pattern left leaves on trees mountain animals, symbols, etc., and there is different print or patterns and there is a local myth about this semiprecious stone .there is chemical acid-base inorganic stone translucent Dendrite Agate(Agate) is Shazar and is also known as Tree Agate(Agate) and Fungus Agate. It is found exclusively in Banda's Ken River. The specialty of the stone is colourful patterns of leaves, trees, mountains, animals, symbols, etc. There is a local myth about Shazar. It is believed that stone prints impression of any object which lies in front of it for a long time. But it's not true. There is a scientific process behind the formation of images on Shazar stone. The patterns we see on shazam are nothing but entrapped fossils of fungus (basic algae). A fungus, which is entrapped between two or more pieces of shazam stone, produces either acid or base. This acid/base makes the stones translucent and acts as inorganic glue which coagulates the separate stones into one. The fossils of fungus left inside the stones look like patterns of leaves or trees and ad beauty to the stone.

Technical Facts About Shazar Stone	
Common Name	Haqiq ,hakeek Tree Agate / Dendrite Agate/ Dendrite Agate/ Ken River Stone
Chemical Configuration	Ca (Mg.Fe.Ae.)[(SiAl ₂)O ₆]
Types of Aggregation	Mon, Granular, Masses, and Short Columnar Crystals triangle prismatic oval heart shape
Colour	Black, Greenish, Brownish and Colourless white orange-brown color in the
Lustre	Vitreous
Density	3.3-3.6
Hardness	6.5-8

The facts provided are based on observation and due to some creative thinking; the interview with Shazar Exporter is based in Banda.

Use: An ordinary useless-looking pebble w, when cleaned and crafted by skilled artisans, becomes a beautiful Hazard stone with the impression that goes beyond imagination A finished & polished stone when set into precious metals become a lady's delight and treasure.

The Variety, quality, and singularity are so that no two stones are similar in any way. Once you have a piece it is rare and only one because nobody can present a duplicate of it. It is mostly used for ornamental purposes like pendants, earrings, rings, and items like paperweights. Pill boxes, sindoordani, etc.

VANISHING Craft:

Banda (India) has the distinction of having National fame craftsmen of Shazar. They have been honored at National and International exhibitions. It is a matter of pride that his stone is crafted only in Banda in India. Banda stone is far better and fine than its only competitor "Montana Dendrite Agate". It has great export potential and can earn foreign enhancement provided proper Govt. help and opportunity to the craftsmen are given.

There was a time the in early 20th century when about workshops and about 200 artisans were involved in the craft. Now there is hardly one-tenth and they too are facing financial and marketing problems. The Raw material; is becoming scarce and costly with increasing production costs and hard bargaining by the old buyers causing this unique craft to disappear forever.

Value:

Though revered and honored everywhere in India and abroad the proper marketing and promotion are yet to beat.

Its market value depends on the size, pattern, and color of the impression on the stone. For more details and trade inquiries you may contact on Frontpage address or telephone numbers.

Literature review

The following literature supports the current study, like the study done by Yadav et al 2020 described the important steps that are useful for the development of this sector of the country this they explained about the import handmade carpet and shazar storne¹. Vanita ahlat 2018 researcher has focused on labor productivity and countries' textile sector" they have discussed in her paper that most of the laborers are women in the textile industry. A study conducted by Roy, Patnaik, and Satpathy (2020) for 690 handicraft industries (Small business) enterprises found a drastic fall in the growth rate (this was due to pandemic Covid -19 of net sales by (-)66.7% in the first quarter of the financial year 2020–21. Yadav et al 2022 discussed a visionary concept of the global handicraft index and role of the role of handicraft artisan and strategies for the development of the. The situation worsened further when the government announced the extended nationwide lockdown amidst the COVID-19 crisis. Anand et. al (2020) highlighted, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)." Resultssuggested that there is enormous gender disparity in employment; that is women are very few in comparison to men workers. Published their research paper "Study of Handicraft Marketing Strategies of Artisans in Uttar Pradesh and Its Implications" as we have discussed the performance of the handicraft sector and the role of women in the handicraft sector is home-based industry. But (Yadav and Tripathi et al 2022) published about the performance of women in ODOP of Uttar Pradesh and they gave an initial approach about the developing global handicraft index for small businesses.

There are about 20 million people that are engaged in Indian sector sectors, and only in the handicraft sector there are 70 lakh workers are involved in the handicraft sector with 6% GDP and 34 % of export in 39 million SSI and 8000 types of handicraft product. "Indian handicrafts" by Kamala Devi Chattopadhyaya 1980 has studied the Indian handicraft product that is related to folk tradition and gentle culture and individual and conceptual work done on regular and development of traditional work.

Khan, W. A, and et al (2013) have described on Handicraft Marketing Strategies of Artisans in Uttar Pradesh and Its Implications and noticed that handicraft sector depends on how well the artisan can produce the article on handicraft and how they introduced it as four P like as place, price, production, and last is promotion. Ritu Agrahari (2017) focused on NGO and government or organizations in the handicraft sector "Role of government and non-government organizations for production and marketing of Chikankaari craft in Luck now.

Objective

- To study the about Shazar stone of Banda Uttar Pradesh and its cultural value in india as well as in gulf countries.
- To study y the problem faced bed by artisans of Banda shazar stone during Covid.

Research methodology

this article is completely based on secondary data that has been taken from different reputed journals and the government of Uttar Pradesh site for this article and GOI ministry of MSME data obtained from 2020 data resource and Bundelkhand district data resources.

Strategy for reviving of Shazar stone

This is very important for the growth of the Indian economy and GDP of the country, but there is a requirement for a better soft cultural policy with other countries because it plays an essential role in the development of handicraft products because it is related to our local tradition and culture, and maximum Indian people are living in most of the country in large number, and they shall popularise their culture and tradition, and there will be aware of their culture in foreign (Yadav et al 2020) .so it is to mandatory for the Indian government to promote the soft cultural policy (Yadav et al 2021) There should be an international expo martin a different country to time by time, an international exhibition of handicraft products in different countries with the help of the EPEH ministry of corporate affair should try to work and provide financial support to the exporter and provide cash awards to them for promotion of handicraft product .and to maintain the capacity of the export of handicraft product in a required country like as gulf country, western country and in USA and Canada.

- Soft cultural policy plays a vital role in the development of the handicraft sector in neighboring as well as other countries. Newspaper and media publication and the security of exporters is our priority for the development of this eminent sector. international exhibition geographical indication GI tag, E-marketing proper information of foreign buyer national and international park and store social media like Facebook, Twitter, Olx, handicraft scholarship international program (Yadav et al 2022)

- There should be a better international relationship between India with other countries because when there is the proper interchange of culture and traditions of one country with another country, then the export of handicraft products will be accessible in those countries. so India must be making a plan and policy to promote the handicraft product in those countries that Ghana is close with our culture and tradition in some countries export-import policy is so strong. India should also follow up on these soft policies related to the handicraft industry.

- Similar to the environment and yoga syllabus, there should be start handicraft syllabus in school education and should be made essential for this and start to be a subject related to the handicraft and cultural and traditions book.

- Newspaper and media should be publishing their local handicraft industry product daily on each product that is famous for that area. In local Mela and Haat or exhibitions, it should be essential and put 60% product of handicrafts with each other. The listing system should be removed entirely for these products in place of the license system there should encourage the development of a certification and regulation system of the tagging process as Local tag should be a priority for the local level. The global tag also called the GI tag to the handicraft product should be based on quality and popular products by which artisan and handicraft owners can feel excitement for the handicraft product (Anirban Dasgupta & Bibhas Chandra, 2016). TV advertisements should be free for their product or at little cost. There is a search for the targeted market in-country and the local area with the ITPO Indian trade promotion organization. It should be an organized buyer-seller to get together meeting at the proper time at local and national and international levels for the development of handicrafts. There should be proper information to a foreign buyer with the help of foreign EPEH, ITPO. It should start the scholarship and fellowship program in the neighboring country, especially for handicraft worker that is expert (Yadav et al. 2021).

7.9 Producer level strategies:

There should be an allow-income tax for handicraft products at the national level. The fund that is obtained by the government should, and 5%of these taxes should be used for the branding of the handicraft product. There should be the proper security of exporter products and providing subsidies and grants to artisans related to the handicraft industries during handmade products are exported, and it should be based on the quality and quantity of the handicraft product. Proper complaining of the P2M promotion and positioning of the market. Supply raw materials should be sufficient and at a reasonable price. There should be up-gradation of the technology and updating of the capacity of the skilled labor. Currently, total export in India is expected to increase by US\$3.8 billion by the financial year 2020-21 (Yadav et al. 2021).

So the handicraft industry is one of the rapidly booming industries with a growth rate of 15%. Known across the globe for its fine tradition, beauty, and culture. There are two critical facts about the Indian handicraft industry; one of the most significant parts of the Indian small-scale industry is the handicraft sector industry. Continuity to explore untapped market digital marketing and the way forward for the handicraft industry to business. Inadequate platforms to advertise and publicized to find a suitable and sustainable market for their respective product. Creating awareness and solving the challenges faced by the handicraft industry (Yadav et al 2022). Government and exporter and to launch media channel by govt and by producer company material in the with your craft business website should be appealing, perceptive and user-friendly storytelling could serve as an essential role in boosting your good business content with an appropriate and impressive image of your craft here are few links to create a better business website. To Use Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Hangout,

Blogs, Instagram, Hike, send on OLX of the handicraft item for promotion and advertise by each people with govt also. To provide better facilities for labor, those are involved in the handicraft work profession (Yadav et al. 2022).

7.10. Artisan and labor (worker) related strategy.

- Satisfactory wages, value to the worker or artisans.
- Proper PF, Bonus, medical facility.
- Financial support to Artisan by Govt. Promotion, Distribution of their Craft in the market.
- Proper leave with payment. Branding of product with artisan name area with heritage product

Proper security reward to artisans.

7.11. Traditional and heritage base strategy:

• Popularise the city with handicraft product, origin region, name of artisan, name of craft it should be special.

• Advertise the temple with its craft origin where it is originated special artisan has to free facility in bus transport services.

- Celebrate the craft fair, and maintain the heritage, and tradition of its local culture.

Problem faced by the handicraft sector (major problem)

1. Scarcity of skilled labor
2. High excise duty
3. Bad infrastructure
4. Lack of transport services
5. Problem of good road connectivity
6. Low interest of the worker
7. Low salary and wages
8. Unstructured market place
9. Uncertainty of power supply
10. Lack of drainage services
11. Irregularity in job
12. Unwilling management
13. Rude behaviour of owner a manager

(Medium problem)

1. Improper finishing of the product.
2. High connectivity with machine-made industry
3. Low speed of single window system
4. Most of the industry is in the village area
5. Lack of public and specific product go down or storage
6. Spreading of cultural policy is slow in India in which. A handmade product is used
7. Lack of better international relations with the debouching country
8. No security of exporter
9. There is nothing or least subsidy or grant for handicrafts product
10. Lack of practical implementation of govt

Mixed

1. Defective marketing in India) (mixed problem)
2. Outdated technique of manufacturing
3. The licensing problem is high in the handicraft area
4. There is nothing branding of handicraft products in or media
5. Nothing exhibition of handicraft products
6. Tag certification is so critical in India
7. Back of market awareness about the handicraft sector
8. There is a fewer training centre
9. Inspector labor inspector disturb the artisan
10. There is nothing financial support
11. Supply of raw materials is difficult in India
12. Product is a global style
13. There is nothing interest of professional in handicraft sector in tersest
14. There is no protection for exporters

7. SWOT analysis

Threat

1. There is high competition in the local and domestic market balance between high demand and supply.

2. There is a variation of quality products produced by competing countries like China, the USA South Africa.

3. There is better trade terms offered by competing countries .and increased and better technological support and rest facilities in competing country 1

STRENGTH

1. Large, diversified, variety and range available,

2. Cheap, labor, rate that Strength

3. There is a large diversified and huge market potential, this is the basic strength of the handicraft sector.

4. In the handicraft sector, there is a large product variety, and range of the handicraft is available has become a diversified culture.

5. There is supportive retail of the infrastructure with strong and diversified.

6. For a better combative price, there is a cheap labor rate.

7. There is a need for low capital investment.

8. There is high production flexibility.

9. There is a low barrier to new entry fo0r the development of the handicraft

Weakness

1lack of infrastructure Lack of infrastructure and communication facility between the customer and artisan related to handicraft.

2. There is an unawareness of national and international requirements and markets in the handicraft sector.

3. There is a continuous lack of coordination between government bodies and the private sector,

4. There is inadequate information about new technology.

5. There is less interest in newcomers and young people in the handicraft industry and also there is a lack of skilled labor and trainer

6. So there is skill confirmed to a rural area and many san small cities and untouched market.

7. There is a lack of promotion of production

Opportunity

1. Rising demand for handicraft products in a fast and developing country. Such.

2. Development of sectors like industry requires a real state that offers great requirement of handicraft product attribution channel.

3. Development of domestic and international tourism sector.

4. E-commerce and the Internet emerge as a promising dis to markets.

Conclusion

The pandemic situation has created more problems for people Even in this tough time of the whole world and millions of the population have been lost they're life due to **Covid** 19. Artisans and worker returned their homes and then engaged in hand-making products that they were adopted from their ancestors. returned to their country, state from own state economy slowdown of the whole world but in this situation, in this situation handicraft sector has potential to provide job and to create and upgrade their skill and start-up at the local level to provide more job to solve the problem. (Yadav et al 2022).

However, the hazard stone industry is suffering more so the government needs to care about this industry so artisans depend on this industry can survive and conserve their tradition, culture, and Indian heritage with sustainable development suffered due to pandemics and seeing unorganized, with the additional constraints of lack of education, low capital, and inadequate exposure to new technologies, absence of market intelligence, and an insufficient institutional framework.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests.

The Author declared none of the conflicts of interest concerning research Authorship and publication of this article.

REFERENCES

1. Al-Dhaafri H.S. and Alasania, M.S. (2020), "Impact of total quality management, organizational excellence and entrepreneurial orientation on organizational performance: empirical evidence from the public sector in UAE", *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 27(9), 2497-2519.25.
2. Anand, Abhishek, Mehrotra, Akash, Gayatri, Manoj Nayak et.al (2020). 'Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs): India report', Microwave Consulting, Lucknow, India
3. Anirban Dasgupta & Bibhas Chandra (2016) *Evolving Motives for Fair Trade Consumption: A*

- Qualitative Study on Handicraft Consumers of India, *The Anthropologist*, 23:3, 414-422, DOI: 10.1080/09720073.2014.11891962
4. Ashish Kumar Singh (2019) Comparative assessment of shift in hearing threshold among handicraft operatives in India, *Ergonomics*, 62:1, 88-102, DOI: 10.1080/00140139.2018.1519121
 5. Ashish Kumar Singh, Makkhan Lal Meena, Himanshu Chaudhary & Govind Sharan Dangayach (2019) A comparative assessment of static muscular strength among female operative's working in different handicraft occupations in India, *Health Care for Women International*, 40:4, 459-478, DOI: 10.1080/07399332.2018.1484468
 6. Ashwani and Pravakar Sahoo, (2020). 'COVID-19 and Indian Economy: Impact on Growth, Craft Council of India (2011), *Craft Economy Impact Study*, www.craftcouncilofindia.
 7. Berkel, René Van (2020), 'India's Manufacturing Reel – the impact of COVID-19' Article Accessed from the Website <https://www.unido.org/stories/indias-manufacturing-reels-impact-covid-19>
 8. Chicherov A. I. (1970) A Contribution to the Description of the Socioeconomic Structure of India on the Eve of the Colonial Conquest: (Handicraft Production from the 17th to the Early 19th Century), *Soviet Studies in History*, 9:2, 133-154, DOI: 10.2753/RSH1061-19830902133
 9. CII (2020). 'CII sets fund for MSME to tackle COVID-19', Article was accessed from website <https://www.manufacturingtodayindia.com/people/6997-cii-sets-up-fund-for-MSME-to-tackle-covid-19-during-10-June-2020>.
 10. Dak, T.M., *Rural Industrialisation: Challenges and Responses*, North Book, Delhi, pp. 23-24 (1989) 4.
 11. Development Commissioner (Handicrafts), Ministry of Textiles, New Delhi.
 12. Florence, K., *Uganda Handicrafts Export Strategy*, ITC Report, WTO (2005).
 13. Gandhimathy, B. (2013). The paper published on "An Economic Analysis of Production Industrial Co-Operatives in Tamil Nadu: The Stochastic Production Function Model" *Arthshastra: Indian Journal of Economics & Research*, 2(6), 40-46.
 14. GoI (2020). 'COVID-19: Finance Commission's advisory panel suggests support to smallbiz, NBFCs', Press Information Bureau, Government of India, Accessed from the website <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1617900>
 15. GoI (2020). *Index of Industrial Production – Monthly*, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. Government of India
 16. GoI (2020). *Registration of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in India (Udyog Aadhaar Memorandum)*, Office of Development Commissioner, Ministry of MSME, Government of India
 17. GoI (Various years). *Annual Reports of the Ministry, DC MSME*, Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Government of India.
 18. *Handmade in India: Geographic Encyclopaedias of India Handicrafts*[Hardcover]
 19. Hannon P, Chaudhuri S. Why the Economic Recovery Will Be More of a Swoosh Than V-Shaped; 2020. *Wall Street Journal*.
 20. <http://www.indiamart.com/unique-handicrafts-delhi/>
 21. Jadhav, S., *Indian Handicrafts: An overview of Growing or Depleting?* IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM).
 22. JafariSadeghi, V., Dutta, D.K., Ferraris, A. and DeGiudice, M. (2020). "Internationalisation business processes in an under-suppo: evidence from Italian SMEs", *Business Process Management Journal*, 26(5), 1055-1074.
 23. Kamla Devi Chattopadhyay (1980) *India's craft tradition*, publication division government of India New Delhi.
 24. Kaviani, M.A., Tavana, M., Kowsari, F. And Rezapour, R. (2020)red policy context. "Supply chain resilience: a benchmarking model for vulnerability and capability assessment in the automotive industry", *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 27(6), 1929-1949.
 25. Khan, W.A, and Amir, Z. *Study of Handicraft Marketing Strategies of Artisans in [2] Uttar Pradesh and Its Implications*, *Research Journal of Management Sciences*, Vol. 2(2), Feb. 2013.
 26. Khurana, S., Haleem, A., Luthra, S., Huisingh, D., & Mannan, B. (2021). "Now is the time to press the reset button: Helping India's companies to become more resilient and effective in overcoming the impacts of COVID-19, climate changes and other crises", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 280(2), 124466.
 27. Lisa M. Grobar (2019) *Policies to promote employment and preserve cultural heritage in the*

- handicraft sector, *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 25:4, 515-527, DOI: 10.1080/10286632.2017.1330887
28. Manufacturing, Trade and MSME Sector' Article accessed from the website: [HTTPS10. journals.sagepub.com/ doi/full/10.1177/0972150920945687](https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0972150920945687).
 29. Mathew, P.M. Employment in Handloom and Handicrafts Sectors, *Yojana*, May 2011.
 30. MinistryofTextiles30-March-2017 18:25 IST
 31. Mohi-us-din, Mir & Bhutan (2014) "A Study of the Impact of Government Policies on Marketing Strategy of Handicrafts".
 32. Planning Commission India (2012) Government of India:
 33. Rajat Kamble, Avinash Sahu & Sangeeta Pandit (2021) Occupational ergonomic assessment of hand pain symptoms among Bagh hand block print artisans of the handicraft textile industry in Madhya Pradesh, India, *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, DOI: 10.1080/10803548.2021.1991131
 34. Report submitted by the ministry of corporate and textile End year report oh handicraft 2018 ministry of corporate and textile 2018.
 35. Rituagrahari 2017 "Role of government and non-government organizations for production and marketing of Chikankari craft in Luck now"
 36. Yadav U.s, Tripathi, R, Tripathi M.A 2020 (Strategies for development of handicraft sector small industries' in India)small enterprises development management and extension journal Sage publication September 2020
 37. Yadav, U. S, Ravindra Tripathi, Mano Ashish Tripathi, Rajesh Kumar Shastri, Gyan Prakash Yadav, & Aliza. (2022). Entrepreneurial Development of Artisan in ODOP in Uttar Pradesh to Boost Economy: Strategies and New Approaches Towards Global Handicraft Index for Socio-Economic Welfare of Artisans. *Asian Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship, and Social Science*, 2(01), 1-17. Retrieved from <http://www.ajmesc.com/index.php/ajmesc/article/view/46>
 38. Yadav, U. S., Tripathi, R., Yadav, G. P., & Tripathi, M. A. (2022). Proposal of a Global Handicraft Index for Sustainable Development: A Visionary Approach for Small Industry and Developing Strategies for Handicraft (Rural Industry). *European Journal of Sustainable Development Research*, 6(2), em0185. <https://doi.org/10.21601/ejosdr/11909>
 39. Yadav, U.S, Tripathi, R., Tripathi, M.A., Rawat, R., & Kushwaha, J. (2022). Performance of women artisans as entrepreneurs in odor in Uttar Pradesh to boost economy: strategies and away towards global handicraft index for small business. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 26(1), 1-19.
 40. Yadav,U, S, Ravindra Tripathi, Mano Ashish Tripathi, Rajesh Kumar Shastri, Gyan Prakash Yadav, & Aliza. (2022) Role of One district one product (ODOP) and Moonz craft of Uttar Pradesh: Strategies and new approaches for developing first Global Handicraft Index. *Bank and Policy*. 2 (2). Baku
 41. Yadav. U.S,Tripathi ,R,Tripathi M.A. Exclusive and Digital analysis of the transformation of Institutions in the knowledge and innovation system of the handmade world carpet industry journal of positive school psychology ,page 1135-1160